

Aviation Inspection GATE

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Automated aircraft inspection

Optimize your maintenance process, reduce workload, increase safety and traceability. We make your visual inspections faster, repeatable and more reliable. We put your aircraft quicker back in the air and reduce AOG time and costs.

European Union
European Regional
Development Fund

INVESTING IN YOUR FUTURE

SZÉCHENYI 2020

Improve the efficiency of your aircraft inspections
We offer an automated solution enabling quick, safe and reliable inspections, combining computer vision technology with an intuitive damage management software.

Technology

We contribute to the modernization of your tools and methods, providing a unique patented technology. We help you to move towards a paperless workflow and support the digitalization of your maintenance process.